

Consciousness: The Phenomenon of Being Part 2: The Study of the Subjective State

I. Introduction: Can Neural Mechanisms contextualize their phenomena?

Consciousness in the brain can be likened to an orchestra. Each distributed neural network on its own plays an instrument (via its electrochemical firing). Their unified coordinated rhythm (or the synchronicity of their oscillations) is what constitutes the fluid cohesive stream of awareness that is vernacularly referred to as “consciousness”. However, explaining the mechanism for the “orchestra” alone does not explain the full picture of subjective awareness. One still needs to explain the mechanism of the “listener” or the “ghost” inside the brain that actually somehow experiences this cohesive “consciousness” brought about by synchronized neuronal oscillations. Essentially this asks - what is the nature of the ghost inside the brain that “experiences” consciousness, the listener that is there to hear the music of the neural orchestra?

One may suggest that this metaphor is faulty as the brain itself is meant to be the “listener” of the orchestra that is the physical universe. This is to say that this metaphor can be seen by some as an example of “Cartesian Theater”. “Cartesian Theater” is a term coined by philosopher Daniel Dennett to explain the problem of localizing consciousness itself to a single entity in the brain. Dennett uses a “theater” metaphor to describe such theories as requiring a conscious “homunculus” type entity inside of the brain to “watch”, makes sense of all of the individual neural processes and then integrate them into a “conscious awareness”. The problem with these types of theories is that if it is the homunculus who is responsible for consciousness, then the homunculus itself must also have a homunculus inside of it who is then responsible for its own consciousness. Therefore, any attempt to attribute consciousness to the perceptions of a “homunculus” inside of the brain make no sense as each homunculus itself would then require its own homunculus to explain its own consciousness resulting in a nonsensical iterative loop where the origin of consciousness could never be explained.

All of that being said, the metaphor of the need for a “listener” to experience the “awareness” brought about by neural processes is significantly different from “Cartesian Theater”. The confusion here comes from an ambiguous definition of consciousness. In Cartesian Theater, individual sensations, perceptions and neural functionalities exist objectively on their own but require a separate entity in the brain to “watch” and integrate all of these functionalities into a fluid cohesive stream of awareness and decision making IE consciousness. However, in the example of the neural orchestra, that mechanism of “conscious awareness” is already fully explained. This is to say that the orchestra itself is not merely a group of individual neural functionalities, but rather already the entire integrated cohesive stream of awareness. Therefore, there is no need for a “homunculus” in the brain to individually integrate all of the neural functionalities together to create “conscious awareness” since that is already explained by the functions of the neural orchestra. The unexplained portion however is not the conscious awareness element, but rather how that conscious awareness is experienced subjectively.

To elaborate, explaining “conscious awareness” as an objective process does not automatically discount the need for explaining how that objective process is experienced by a subjective entity. To illustrate this, suppose that consciousness as a whole is merely a neural process that can be explained purely objectively like any other process in the universe. This would make the entire

universe, both its observers and observations essentially just a block of objective “content”. If there were only this “block” of content, how could the sheer notion of subjectivity have ever arisen? For if this were true, the universe should simply always exist as a whole and never have any of its objective processes contextualized in the form of subjective perspectives. Neural activity can account for awareness sure, but can the process of awareness alone explain the contextualization of that awareness? While deceptively intuitive, a mechanism for “subjectivity” itself should not be ignored in a universe where everything is claimed to be empirically objective. Perhaps the real issue here is that subjectivity is so fundamental to our experience that there is a tendency to think of it as intuitive and not needing to be explained.

Another school of thought called “Illusionism” posits that this “subjective context” itself is an illusion and that “subjective experience” itself does not exist. Illusionists say that the “illusion” of subjective experience is simply a byproduct of evolution to allow the brain to represent a “space” for enhanced decision making and cognition. Subjectivity in this sense is simply the byproduct of the “broadcasting” of these processes throughout the brain but is actually objectively non-existent on its own. The logic to illusionism states that as more and more mechanisms of neural processes are discovered, it is becoming clear that every faction of consciousness (including the subjectivity) could be explained in such a manner. In this way it therefore essentially regards the whole universe as an “objective observation” and denies the existence of illusive subjective “observers”.

The issue with illusionism is the following: Since the entire universe itself only ever exists as observations of observers, to deny the existence of the observer is to also deny the existence of the universe. For one can’t state “I know the universe exists as a fundamental objective whole” and then also state that “I am just an objective figment of the universe”. If there is no subjective contextualization to that objective universe, there is no reason why that “conscious figment” should ever have its own separate experience from the rest of the universe at all. As stated earlier, if everything is “objective content” there should be no arbitrary separations in that content. Contextualization is therefore required to explain how segments of that objective universe could take on their own subjective existences.

Again, explaining the mechanism of consciousness objectively does not explain how a subjective context is created within it separate from the “rest” of the external universe it subsequently experiences. Herein lies the need for a “listener” of the orchestra, a subjective context from which “conscious awareness” can actually be contextualized. However, this listener does not “listen” with its ear, requiring its own cochlea and auditory cortex, but rather listens simply as existing as an avenue for contextualization of a part of the universe as something that is separate from everything else. The mechanism for this “listener” or subjective context is therefore a different problem than the mechanism for the actual fluid cohesive stream of experience known as ‘conscious awareness’. While it is true that neural processes can explain the mechanism of ‘conscious awareness’, explaining the mechanism of the contextual ‘listener’ remains a much taller task.

Trying to explain how objective neural mechanisms construct this “listener” may be akin to trying to dissect a telephone in order to discover the true nature of the person on the other side. One may be successful in determining how the telephone reproduces sound but fail in realizing that

there exists another physical person outside of the telephone. This metaphor is not meant to illustrate that there exists an ethereal “soul” outside of the brain, but rather that the current understanding of science is still in its infancy and may lack the tools necessary to explain the total integration of the physical universe and its observers or what I refer to as ‘Experia’. It is therefore presumptuous to assume that the fundamental nature of all of “Experia” is included in the “toolbox” of contemporary neuroscientific knowledge. For this reason, searching for the origin of subjectivity via its supposed “neural correlates” may prove to be futile utilizing the current approach. As mentioned previously, the neural correlates are not correlates of subjectivity but rather correlates of awareness. Just because subjectivity seems to only be objectively exposed in its underlying of awareness, does not mean that the two are one and the same.

2. Examining the Plausibility of Subjective Unaware states

The proposal here is that “subjective context” may be an entity on its own entirely independent of mental awareness and thus not influenced by any neural mechanism. Assuming that such a quantifiable subjective context (or QsC) on its own exists, multiple questions arise. The first of these being - how is it possible that subjective contexts are separate from awareness if they are only ever known to be experienced while aware? Since there is no record of “subjective context” being experienced outside of any aware state (dreaming, alert etc), how is it possible that it can exist as a separate independent entity? The second question would be - what would a subjective state without awareness look like if it is true the two can exist independent of each other?

2A. Can one Detect their own Subjective Unaware States?

Since individuals are only able to recall instances of their past subjective states via memory retrieval, they would be unable to recall any state when their brain wasn’t encoding memories. This doesn’t mean that they wouldn’t ever experience subjective unaware states but rather that when they did they wouldn’t subsequently remember them as they were never encoded into memory. Furthermore, since any means of analysis requires awareness, there would be no means for one to ever measure these states in real time. Inability to ever analyze these states coupled with a lack of memory therefore render subjective unaware states impossible to ever be “realized” by their own observers. For this reason, if as listeners there was ever a time where subjective contexts weren’t able to hear the orchestra of neural mechanisms, it is still nevertheless plausible that they’d be “listening” just not hearing something as complex as an orchestra or recording it.

2B. Can Subjective Unaware States be Detected in Others?

Objectively, while external observers could technically determine when an individual is “unaware” there is no way for them to measure when an individual is experiencing a subjective state while unaware. Again, studying those experiencing altered states of consciousness such as during dreaming or while on psychoactive substances only measures how they function with different non-zero levels of awareness, but does not measure the subjective state without any awareness. It essentially just measures the functionality of the neural orchestra when instruments are tuned differently and still says nothing about the “listener”. The difficulty here

is that the subjective context of consciousness would not necessarily change across any state of awareness no matter whether one be sleeping, dreaming, psychoactively affected or alert. This is to say that without the element of awareness and memory one can only assume that subjectivity is constant throughout all aware states since there is nothing to suggest otherwise. The diagrams below show how different states of awareness would be affected by the frequency of neural activity versus how subjectivity would be if the two are functionally independent.

Once establishing that “Subjective Unaware States” are at least plausible the question then becomes what an imagined subjective unaware state would be like. As it stands there are currently only two mainstream hypotheses that relate to the question of the phenomenal aspects of consciousness - traditional panpsychism and the integrated information theory.

3. Existing Viewpoints of Subjective States

3A. The Traditional Panpsychist View

According to traditional panpsychism, subjectivity is simply a fundamental property of physical matter and is therefore present across every subatomic particle. Therefore, every iota of objective content in the universe possesses an elusive but fundamental property of subjectivity allowing that iota to be contextualized. According to panpsychism, while the subjectivity of a human brain would be layered with the functionalities of cognition and awareness, something like a stone on the other hand would lack these features but still nevertheless have its own subjective sense of existence no matter how simple that may be. For according to panpsychism even inanimate objects would have ‘experiences’ even if those experiences did not allow them view or interact with the outside world in a meaningful way.

While different sectors of panpsychism disagree on what such subjective unaware states would look like in humans, it is fair to assume that when there is no level of awareness (IE coma, deep sleep or even death) there would still exist a subjective experiences for each subatomic particle that makes up the body. While there would be no “brain” to cohesively integrate an “awareness” atop these individual subjective states, base subjectivity on the individual particle

level would nevertheless be maintained. This consciousness would therefore have no access to any of its memories or have the ability to interface with the outside world but would still have a feeling of 'being' even if the feeling lacks any awareness and is just a base feeling of 'existence'. Therefore, per traditional panpsychism, after one dies their consciousness would continue but not in the aware attentive nature it did while they were living but rather as a mere semblance of being.

Perhaps the most infamous shortcoming of traditional panpsychism is its inability to explain the "combination problem" which questions how individual "subjective" components of matter are able to combine into "whole" systems of subjective states. This is to ask how indivisible subatomic particles can each constitute their own subjective existences while at the same make up a "brain" where a single subjectivity is present throughout.

While there are many approaches to resolving this, the main issue with the question involves assigning the properties of awareness to those of subjectivity. This is to say that just because a brain utilizes a multitude of coordinated systems to exhibit one cohesive awareness does not mean that there do not exist multiple individual subjectivities that underlie that awareness. This is to suggest that multiple subjective contexts are perceived as a whole only when the brain overlays them with the functionalities of awareness.

Another possible solution to the combination problem is to say that every possible combination of every possible fundamental particle results in a single cohesive subjectivity that could then utilize the resources of the physical properties of said matter (An example of this would be multiple subjective contexts of fundamental properties combining in the brain to form a single instance of subjective awareness utilizing the brains functional properties). This would mean that there are really a vast number of different subjective experiences that make up every 'person' even if only one is experienced at a time. While this is an interesting idea, it would be intuitively inefficient for every combination of every system to have its own subjective state.

3B. The Integrated Information Theory

Integrated Information Theory posits that consciousness as a whole is dependent on the degree of integrated information in a system. Integrated information is essentially synchronized information that is projected unto oneself and differs from non-integrated information which does not "loop" information in this way. IIT also specifically defines consciousness by the possession of set qualities or what it refers to as 'axioms'. These axioms include existence (the fact that consciousness exists phenomenally), composition (the notion that consciousness is comprehensively structured by its use of schemas, objects and notions), information (explains that consciousness accesses and deals with specific information in the form of perceptions and judgments), integration (consciousness is experienced as a total whole) and exclusion (consciousness is experienced one experience at a time).

While IIT does not directly deal with the question of subjective states it implies that such states wouldn't necessarily differ from awareness since they are both dependent on the degree of integrated information in a system. Assumedly, subjective states without typical awareness could technically exist per IIT but would nevertheless have to satisfy the theory's axioms.

Therefore per the theory, one would never experience 'nothing' but rather a manifestation of all integrated information that exists within an individual system given the base axioms are met. IIT also introduces degrees of consciousness based on a metric it refers to as 'Phi' which measures the total amount of integrated information present in a system or the amount of information a system can reflect upon itself. Once Phi is high enough and exceeds a specific threshold, the axioms of consciousness are present in a system and the system is considered 'consciousness'. If the amount of integrated information in a system does not exceed this threshold, "consciousness" would not be present.

If one views the universe as an objective block of content, then according to IIT subjectivity itself would not be 'separate' from that content but actually exist as a property of that content. For when the degree of integrated information in an individual segment of that block exceeds a certain threshold known as "phi", that isolated segment of content develops its own subjective context. This explains why the human brain which ensembles a high degree of "phi" has a substantive consciousness while other "complex" systems that aren't as integrated may not. It also accounts for why consciousness is experienced during synchronous and integrated wakeful states vs. while asleep and other unconscious states.

While the Integrated Information theory is interesting and theoretically impressive, it is still in its infancy in terms of its ability to fully explain how consciousness actually arises from integrated information. While some of its axioms could undoubtedly be explained by neural processes (such as the composition and integration of consciousness), it does not provide a specific mechanism for the phenomenal aspects of consciousness other than its base idea that it is somehow dependent on integrated information.

Furthermore, traditional panpsychism also does not explain the mechanism for how "subjectivity" exists besides for it being a fundamental element of all iotas in the universe. This is to say, it still fails to provide a mechanism for how these properties work and what causes them. Therefore, while both IIT and traditional panpsychism provide interesting general frameworks in explaining subjective contexts, they generally fail in providing detailed mechanisms for how the underlying processes that make up such as a framework would work.

4. Conclusion

As stated earlier, there is a tendency for contemporary scientists to scoff at theories that place any aspect of consciousness outside current neurophysical frameworks. This derision actually comes from a good place as psychologically people have a tendency to ascribe unexplainable supernatural forces to processes that aren't explained by the scientific consensus of their times. However, just because that instinct exists, does that mean that the alternative should be to simply "cling" to current frameworks with the hope that they account for every single mystery that exists? After all, every single major view of the universe before the twentieth century is now regarded as either utterly false or incomplete. Is it so nonsensical to think that the current scientific consensus won't be considered the same in 100-200 years? Isn't it at least plausible to say that at the very least the current framework is most likely not capable of explaining every single phenomena present in our experiences? This is not to say that rational mechanisms for processes such as "subjective contextualization" do not exist and are simply "magical" or

metaphysical. Rather, it is simply to state that all ideas on the matter should be taken seriously and evaluated on their empirical merits regardless of if they fall into current neurophysical frameworks. It is actually the “clinging” to contemporary frameworks that has historically held back the progress of science in general with the most notable example being the clergy’s war on empiricism that expanded the dark ages. The point here is that subjectivity itself should not be disregarded as metaphysical simply because it doesn’t align with the current consensus of physical sciences. At the same time, the solution to the “subjectivity problem” should not be to simply state that potential “theories of subjectivity” aren’t subject to empirical scrutiny since they exist in a different “unexplainable” realm of ideologies. For even unexplainable “magic” is not magic but just technology with unexplained mechanisms. Therefore, elusive as it may seem, there do exist mechanisms for the unexplained phenomena of “subjective context” whether they be explained through current neurophysical frameworks, traditional panpsychism, the integrated information theory or some other system altogether. Ultimately the point is this: to every mystery there is a mechanism, and to deny any mystery only hinders the pursuit of knowledge.